

Viscosity *B*-Coefficients of Sucrose and Urea in Dimethyl Sulphoxide + Water Mixtures

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Earlier we reported^{1,2} the volumetric and viscometric properties of some electrolytes in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) and DMSO + H₂O mixtures. However, no useful studies have been carried out to ascertain the behaviour of non-electrolytes, sucrose and urea in particular, in DMSO + H₂O mixtures. The reason for the choice of this kind of solutions is due to the fact that remarkable variations in behaviour of solute are found when the solvent system changes from pure water to systems containing small quantities of organic co-solvent³.

Results and Discussion

The relative viscosity and density of sucrose and urea in 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25% (by weight) of DMSO + H₂O binary mixtures have been determined at 303 K. It has been assumed that the relative viscosity of non-electrolytes in binary aqueous organic solvents like DMSO + H₂O may be represented by the Jones-Dole equation⁴,

$$\eta_{rel} = \eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1)$$

where, η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and solvent (DMSO + H₂O) respectively, C is the molar concentration of the solute, and other terms have their usual significance. According to equation (1), the straight-line plots should be obtained if $(\eta_{rel}-1)/\sqrt{C}$ is plotted against \sqrt{C} . Such plots for both the non-electrolytes were found to be linear, without scatter. The A and B values (Table 1) were calculated by the least-squares method by fitting the experimental results in Jones-Dole equation (1) (Table 1). The results show increasing A (positive) values and decreasing B values for both the solutes in the entire composition range of DMSO + H₂O at 303 K, suggesting an increase in solute-solute interactions and decrease in solute-solvent interactions with increase in DMSO.

dB/dT , known to be a better criterion⁵ for determining the structure-making/breaking nature of any solute, has been studied for both the solutes in 5% DMSO + H₂O only (Table 1). dB/dT has been found to be positive for both the solutes, thereby suggesting the solutes to behave as structure-breakers.

The viscosity data have also been analysed on the basis of transition state theory. $\Delta\mu_2^{o\ddagger}$, the contribution per mole of solute to the free energy of activation for viscous flow of solution, has been determined using equation (2), as sug-

TABLE 1—VALUES OF A (cm^{3/2} mol^{-1/2}) AND B (cm³ mol⁻¹) PARAMETERS FOR SUCROSE AND UREA IN DMSO + H₂O MIXTURES

Parameter	DMSO% (w/w)				
	5	10	15	20	25
Sucrose in DMSO + H ₂ O at 303 K					
A	0.272 (0.001) ^a	0.336 (0.001)	0.369 (0.005)	0.394 (0.001)	0.414 (0.003)
B	0.480 (0.004) ^a	0.475 (0.006)	0.445 (0.003)	0.432 (0.003)	0.425 (0.011)
Urea in DMSO + H ₂ O at 303 K					
A	0.330 (0.001) ^a	0.420 (0.001)	0.494 (0.002)	0.569 (0.001)	0.642 (0.004)
B	-0.532 (0.006) ^a	-0.616 (0.001)	-0.693 (0.009)	-0.812 (0.007)	-0.929 (0.007)
Temp (K)					
303 308 313 318					
Sucrose in 5% DMSO + H ₂ O					
A	0.480 (0.004) ^a	0.602 (0.007)	0.753 (0.002)	0.935 (0.015)	
Urea in 5% DMSO + H ₂ O					
B	-0.532 (0.006) ^a	-0.493 (0.002)	-0.433 (0.003)	-0.427 (0.007)	

^aStandard errors are given in parentheses.

gested by Feakins *et al.*⁶,

$$\Delta\mu_2^{o\ddagger} = \Delta\mu_1^{o\ddagger} + \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^o} \left[1000B - (\bar{V}_1^o - \bar{V}_1^o) \right] \quad (2)$$

Where, \bar{V}_1^o and \bar{V}_2^o are the partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute respectively. $\Delta\mu_1^{o\ddagger}$, the free energy of activation per mole of the pure solvent, is given by equation (3),

$$\Delta\mu_1^{o\ddagger} = \Delta G_1^o = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^o / hN) \quad (3)$$

here h is the Plank constant, N the Avogadro number, η_0 the viscosity of pure solvent.

For the mixed solvents, each solvent mixture was treated as a pure solvent and the molar volume was calculated as described elsewhere³. The values of \bar{V}_1^o for different DMSO + H₂O mixtures and \bar{V}_2^o , the partial molar volumes at infinite dilution, determined from density data⁷, are given in Table 2. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{o\ddagger}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{o\ddagger}$ estimated using equations (3) and (2), are also given in Table 2. The value of $\Delta\mu_1^{o\ddagger}$ is held practically constant in the entire range of

solvent composition at 303 K. $\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ may be determined in fact by B -coefficient and $(\bar{V}_1^o - \bar{V}_2^o)$ term. It is also evident from Table 2 that $\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ changes with solvent composition at 303 K. The decrease of $\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ with DMSO content suggests that the flow rate is favoured by the DMSO content in the solvent. This supports the previous conclusion from dB/dT .

TABLE 2—VALUES OF DENSITY, VISCOSITY, \bar{V}_1^o , $\Delta\mu_1^{of}$, \bar{V}_2^o AND $\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ FOR SUCROSE AND UREA IN DMSO + H₂O MIXTURES AT 303 K

Parameter	DMSO% (w/w)				
	5	10	15	20	25
Density (g cm ⁻³) 1.028 4	1.002 2	1.009 1	1.014 6	1.023 1	
Viscosity (cP) 1.407 5	0.844 9	1.026 6	1.130 3	1.263 6	
\bar{V}_1^o (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	18.68	19.33	20.02	20.80	21.67
$\Delta\mu_1^{of}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	9.26	9.84	10.00	10.38	10.74
Sucrose in DMSO + H ₂ O					
\bar{V}_2^o (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	322.72	295.45	272.41	247.06	221.85
$\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	114.99	107.73	97.75	90.10	83.42
Urea in DMSO + H ₂ O					
\bar{V}_2^o (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	62.98	61.55	59.85	58.30	56.63
$\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-56.51	-64.94	-72.19	-83.42	-93.19

The various parameters in 5% DMSO + H₂O mixture at different temperatures are given in Table 3. The data show that $\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ value for sucrose increases with increase of temperature. Thus the solute activation entropy increment for viscous flow at infinite dilution is negative, thereby suggesting that the attainment of transition state is associated with a increase in order and thus increases the strength

TABLE 3—VALUES OF DENSITY, VISCOSITY, \bar{V}_1^o , $\Delta\mu_1^{of}$, ΔH_1^{of} , $T\Delta S_1^{of}$, \bar{V}_2^o , $\Delta\mu_2^{of}$, ΔH_2^{of} AND $T\Delta S_2^{of}$ FOR SUCROSE AND UREA IN 5% DMSO + H₂O MIXTURE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Parameter	Temp. (K)			
	303	308	313	318
Density (g cm ⁻³)	1.002 2	1.000 7	0.999 6	0.998 6
Viscosity (cP)	0.844 9	0.768 3	0.696 2	0.629 2
\bar{V}_1^o (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	18.68	18.70	18.72	18.74
$\Delta\mu_1^{of}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	9.26	9.18	9.07	8.95
ΔH_1^{of} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	16.23	16.26	16.27	16.26
$T\Delta S_1^{of}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	6.969	7.084	7.199	7.314
Sucrose in 5% DMSO + H ₂ O				
\bar{V}_2^o (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	322.72	354.78	380.61	414.34
$\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	114.99	137.64	164.05	196.67
ΔH_2^{of} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-982	-999	-1015	-1031
$T\Delta S_2^{of}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-991	-1007	-1024	-1040
Urea in 5% DMSO + H ₂ O				
\bar{V}_2^o (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	62.98	81.60	95.77	110.30
$\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-56.51	-49.85	-40.58	-39.22
ΔH_2^{of} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	330	335	341	346
$T\Delta S_2^{of}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	321	326	332	337

of the binding force. On the other hand, in case of urea, the negative value of $\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ diminishes with increase in temperature and thus the solute activation entropy increment is positive, thereby suggesting that the attainment of transition state is associated with decrease in order and thus decreases the strength of binding force.

The values of B -coefficient at different temperatures can also be used to calculate the activation entropy from the relation⁶,

$$d(\Delta\mu_2^{of})/dT = -\Delta S_2^{of} \quad (4)$$

The values of $\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ have been calculated from the slopes of linear plots of $\Delta\mu_2^{of}$ versus T and the corresponding $T\Delta S_2^{of}$ values for both solutes in 5% DMSO + H₂O mixture, are given in Table 3.

The activation enthalpy, ΔH_2^{of} has been calculated by using the relation,

$$\Delta H_2^{of} = \Delta\mu_2^{of} + T\Delta S_2^{of} \quad (5)$$

and the corresponding values are also recorded in Table 3. It is also evident that both ΔH_2^{of} and $T\Delta S_2^{of}$ are negative for sucrose, thereby suggesting that the transition state is associated with bond-formation and increase in order. On the other hand, the values of ΔH_2^{of} and $T\Delta S_2^{of}$ are positive for urea, thereby suggesting that the formation of transition state is associated with decrease in order, bond-breaking and distortion of intermolecular bonds.

Experimental

Sucrose and urea (AnalaR) were used as such after drying over P₂O₅ in a desiccator. Dimethyl sulphoxide was purified as described earlier¹. Triple-distilled water (sp. cond. 10⁻⁶ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹) was freshly prepared. The various compositions of DMSO + H₂O mixtures were made by weight. All the solutions of non-electrolytes were also made by weight and conversion of molality into molarity was done by using the standard expression⁸.

Kinetic viscosity was measured at the desired temperature (accuracy ± 0.01°) using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer, calibrated with distilled water at the desired temperature. Runs were repeated until three successive determinations were obtained within ± 0.1 s. The flow time for distilled water was found to be 488.3 s at 303 K. Because all the flow times were greater than 100 s, the kinetic energy correction was not necessary. The relative viscosities of solutions were calculated using the relation,

$$\eta_{rel} = \eta/\eta_o = d/d_o t_o \quad (6)$$

where the terms have their usual significance. For density measurements, an apparatus similar to the one reported by Ward and Millero⁹ and described elsewhere¹⁰ (accuracy in density measurements, ± 1 × 10⁻⁴ g cm⁻³) was used. The density and viscosity measurements were carried out in a

NOTE

water-bath having built-in control system, and the data were reproducible upto four significant figures.

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